

ARCHIVOR

ARCHIVING AND PRESERVATION FOR RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS

White Paper

On behalf of:

ARCHIVER Consortium (CERN, EMBL-EBI, DESY, PIC, Addestino & TRUST-IT)

EMBL-EBI

addestino
innovation delivered.

Trust-IT Services
Communicating ICT to markets

& ARCHIVER Pilot Phase Lead Contractors (Arkivum, LIBNOVA)

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Disclaimer

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Creating value through Data Preservation, every step of the way

Data has both a value and a cost and modern Research Data Management makes many promises in terms of capacity, scalability, ease-of-use and security.

The stewardship of research data involves not only all data-related tasks during the active lifetime of a project itself, but also preparing and associated products for later re-use. The period during which research data remains valuable can stretch into decades.

Many of these research projects cannot yet manage their data, as the archiving and preservation services are inadequate and fall below expectations while data stewardship costs after projects end, are frequently underestimated during the planning phase.

ARCHIVER's[1] main goal was to fulfill many of these data management promises in a multi-disciplinary environment, allowing each research group to retain ownership and the intellectual control of their data whilst leveraging best practices, standards and economies of scale. The combination of multiple ICT technologies, including extreme data-scaling, advanced metadata management, network connectivity, software interoperability and business models, allowed the project to deliver sustainable end-to-end archival and preservation services that cover the full research lifecycle.

The use-cases driving the ARCHIVER consortium's need for Research and Development of innovative data preservation services extended the preservation ecosystems of research organizations to create more dynamic solutions to be deployed primarily by using a hybrid model, on-premise or exclusively in cloud environments, operated by European SMEs that were enhanced and assessed against best practices such of CoreTrustSeal and DPC RAM, so that datasets remain **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)** for decade timescales or more.

One of the main benefits of such a hybrid FAIR approach is that it can be implemented in a transparent way to data producers and (re-)users. This transparency addresses issues that can cross disciplines and national boundaries of the datasets (the F and I) allowing rationalization of resources and cost reduction.

At the time the present white paper is being produced, there is no large-scale production usage yet of commercial data preservation services by the public research sector. The potential uptake for the services resulting from ARCHIVER are many-fold, including supporting the needs of ESFRI[2] and related Research Infrastructures as well as the results of short-term research projects funded at the regional, national and European-level. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)[3] is a major European undertaking providing the outcomes of ARCHIVER with a privileged engagement channel via its catalog and marketplace, making them available to Europe's research communities who seek reliable and scalable solutions that satisfy the obligations of data management plans required by funding agencies.

The focus must be Data, set to live for longer than any vendor, system or technology.

Executive Summary

ARCHIVER was a H2020 co-funded pre-commercial procurement project that produced R&D over 3 years to design, prototype and pilot services for Long-Term Data Preservation in a hybrid cloud environment covering the full research lifecycle for multiple research domains.

The work accomplished in ARCHIVER is considered a game-changer for the approach taken to long-term Research Data Management both from a mindset and technological perspective, i.e. what data do researchers retain, how to keep intellectual control of it and what data stewards must do to ensure long-term value can be realized from it.

This paper provides an overview of the R&D methodology used to achieve its results as well as a technical deep dive of the ARCHIVER outputs, Arkivum and LIBNOVA with concrete examples of the transformational nature of the achieved benefits both for public funded research and the European SME sector.

By working directly with the public research sector, Arkivum and LIBNOVA were able to receive ongoing input and feedback into product development globally serving the use cases of scientific research within Europe.

The innovative format of ARCHIVER, with regular and extensive R&D validation from the public research sector organizations, enabled Arkivum and LIBNOVA to quickly and effectively develop fit-for-purpose products. This has resulted in innovative commercialisation approaches for the resulting services, improving their degree of FAIRness as an aspect of utmost importance for the ultimate objective of reuse of research data.

The services resulting from the ARCHIVER R&D are addressing the gaps that put data at long-term risk and prevent the construction and operation of sustainable Trusted Digital Repository services, affecting organizations both large and small who are tasked with being custodians of valuable research artifacts.

Thanks to its outstanding results, the ARCHIVER project has been recognized by the international community and been awarded by the International Council on Archives, category for Collaboration and Cooperation, at the DPC awards ceremony in Glasgow, on the 12th of September 2022.

The model developed in ARCHIVER is considered very beneficial for the research community. It contributes to address concerns about sharing and re-use of FAIR data to reproduce research, as a pillar for Open Science and long-term preservation of the EOSC federated data, by delivering sustainable, production quality Long-Term Data Preservation services for user communities that fills a gap in the existing European Open Science Cloud portfolio.

FAIR, the importance of Data Preservation in Research

The importance and economic benefits of making scientific data open and reusable according to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) have already been demonstrated. The Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) has completed a study on EOSC, FAIR, and digital preservation, '*FAIR Forever? Long Term Data Preservation Roles and Responsibilities*'[4], commissioned by the EOSC Sustainability Working Group back in 2020. The study highlights the foundational aspects of FAIR guiding principles for the EOSC implementation and the importance of data sharing and re-use in the EOSC, as a “Web” of federated data and services, where aspects intrinsically related to sustainability needed more substantial work still to be performed. The EOSC SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda)[5] reinforces the criticality of these aspects on how the EOSC is conceived: an holistic view of researchers, data and services; research data has meaning only if its provenance, quality and usage are shared; detailed metadata is required to enable the F and R of FAIR; data preservation is not limited to data itself but to all its associated products such as software and documentation; stakeholders must have clear responsibility in ensuring FAIR in the outset and must be identified persistently.

The SRIA also promotes innovative services to be developed using the Pre-Commercial Procurement/Public Procurement of Innovation Solutions (PCP/PPI) co-funding financial instruments for services to be co-developed with the private sector, procured jointly by public authorities and commercialized via the EOSC marketplace.

One of the reasons why ARCHIVER was created is the wide recognition there are still major gaps when it comes to the sustainability of solutions for long-term accessibility and usability of research data, putting data at long-term risk. These gaps are part of the aspects the ARCHIVER project has set out to address by selecting European SME companies with expertise in open data, archiving and data preservation to develop innovative solutions. The ARCHIVER selected SMEs experts that progressed through to the different project phases, Arkivum and LIBNOVA, are promoting services that can support a range of organizations to take steps to respond to the challenge of long-term archival and preservation and provide long-term access to scientific data in a way that:

- is cost-effective at scale when working with very large datasets;
- ensures environmental sustainability by minimizing the carbon footprint of long-term archiving and data access;
- applies good practice in digital preservation and archiving so that datasets remain FAIR;

Part 1: The ARCHIVER model to approach the problem

The R&D Methodology

ARCHIVER spent three years developing innovative services for Long Term Digital Preservation of scientific datasets using the Pre-Commercial Procurement instrument[6]. R&D was performed competitively by commercial suppliers, across different implementation phases.

The services were developed competitively by Arkivum and LIBNOVA co-designed with input from research clusters members: CERN, EMBL-EBI, PIC/IFAE and DESY are members of the ESCAPE cluster[7], DESY is also a partner in the ExPaNDs[8] cluster, while EMBL-EBI is a member of EOSC-Life[9].

These research performing organizations deployed use cases from Astrophysics, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences and Photon-Neutron Sciences[10].

The project started with a preparation phase consisting in a Open Market Consultation (OMC) process back in 2019 to scope the R&D challenge and to improve the mutual understanding of the R&D challenges across the public research organizations partners of the project and industry. Another strategic objective of the preparation phase was to ensure the required visibility, engagement and sufficient interest generation in the R&D tender being prepared.

Figure 1. - R&D challenge definition and scoping based on the dialogue with SMEs.

The preparation phase was evolutionary and consisted in three main components:

- ☁ Production of a state-of-the-art analysis of the digital preservation and archiving services currently available on the market[11] coming both from the demand and supply side, helping to scope project R&D and identify key lessons learned from other initiatives in the field, to be applied in ARCHIVER.
- ☁ Organization of a set of landscaping activities that permitted identifying the potential beneficiaries of the project at large and assess their requirements in terms of digital archiving and preservation. Examples

of these activities were for example liaising with the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC), promote the participation in EOSC related activities or even collaboration with GÉANT network[12] connectivity and Federated Identity Management experts.

☁ Scope the R&D to be produced by assessing and establishing the baseline for the realistic technological innovation potential of archiving and data preservation services within the project scope.

The OMC events promoted a dialog between potential tenderers and open to end-users, located in different countries to encourage participation from both local companies and end-users. These events were preceded by two preparation workshops, hosted by DESY and CERN, where the public research organization representatives, partners of the project performed a first analysis scoping of the project's requirements.

The R&D scoping (Figure 1.) was extremely beneficial as it resulted from bringing together more than 240 people and 40 European companies, including SMEs specialized in the digital and preservation sector and cloud services providers. Recordings of the events were made available on the project website[13].

Following the market consultation process, a Request for R&D Tenders has been published allowing potential tenderers to be as informed as possible, raising awareness about the requirements at a very early stage of the tender publication. The PCP Tender has been executed across different phases of the project (Design, Prototype and Pilot) in a competitive manner, as a "Hunger Games" where firms were selected or and qualified for the next phase or eliminated (Figure 2.).

Figure 2. - ARCHIVER "Hunger Games" methodology.

The methodology warrants that the tender process including call-off (mini-competition) preparation and bid evaluation for each phase transition is put in place and followed correctly, producing the necessary continuous assessments at the end of each of the phases.

The R&D Phases

After scoping the project and executing the R&D tender, the project entered into R&D execution. From a total of 15 initial R&D bids, 5 were selected to produce architectural designs, 3 selected to produce prototypes and then finally 2 were selected to produce pilot services to be ready for general use by the end of the project.

The approach taken for the competitive R&D phases during ARCHIVER consisted in setting up a Quality Assurance process to ensure validation of the innovation produced by the project as it was released. After establishing the baseline of the state of the art capabilities of services offered by each company during the Design Phase, R&D execution started during the ARCHIVER Prototype Phase and continued to the Pilot Phase. R&D was monitored using agile project management tools and a scrum methodology was implemented based on the organization of 2-week sprints (Figure 3) during the R&D phases.

Sprint Start	Number
1st Feb 2021	Sprint 1
15th Feb 2021	Sprint 2
1st Mar 2021	Sprint 3
...	...
12th July 2021	Sprint 12

Figure 3: Sprint schedule example held on the Prototype Phase.

Each sprint included technical meetings between the future buyers (public sector organizations) and the selected companies, ensuring exactly the same treatment, preventing any unfair advantages. Unilateral meetings happened as necessary strictly to provide clarifications about the specificities of use-cases.

One member of the project team, representing the public sector organizations involved, has acted as the 'Scrum Master' organizing the creation of tickets, the coordination the review of each sprint and the preparation of upcoming work. An example of a ticket created is shown below in Figure 4.

The screenshot shows a Jira issue page for the 'Arkivum_Pilot' project, issue 'APIL-51'. The issue title is 'As EMBL-EBI I want to control the export of archived datasets.' The page is divided into several sections: 'Description', 'Steps', and 'Notes'. The 'Description' section explains that EMBL-EBI wants to control the export of archived datasets, which are often held for 30 years and not accessed in the last 25 years. It notes that neither outside users (external to EMBL-EBI) nor internal users (data service operators) will have direct access to the data stored in Arkivum, and they will not be able to perform exports themselves. Only data service operators can request export of a dataset, and this needs to be approved by an EMBL-EBI archival service administrator. The 'Steps' section lists three main steps: 1. Control the amount of dissemination storage required. 2. Control the cost of exporting data. 3. An archiver administrator either: 3a. Approves the request. 3b. Denies the request. The 'Notes' section states that EMBL-EBI is looking to use existing Arkivum features for this where possible, as they know this has been a very late alteration to the use case. They can prioritize adapting the use case to existing features rather than any new features requests in this Pilot phase of the project.

Figure 4. - Typical atomic use case to validate R&D progress.

The sprints created a regular structure of planning and review of the R&D effort that made both sides (public sector and selected companies) very aware of each other's expectations and schedule. It also allowed all parties to adjust the planned work in the light of new information or realizations about use cases and functionality, as revealed by ongoing hands-on prototyping.

These adjustments included the discovery and resolution of technical problems together with the exploitation of opportunities to create valuable features that were not apparent when the R&D work began.

As well as a set of basic functionality tests (e.g. upload/download files), based on manual or automated workflows, each public sector organization provided specific tests documented in a Quality Assurance (QA) plan (part of the Tender specification material).

An example of a QA test from CERN is shown below in Figure 5.

1.3 Open Data Portal Use Case

1.3.1 Integrity checksum

Test Type (Manual/automated)	Support for community-specific data integrity checksum algorithms (automated) http://opendata.cern.ch/
General Purpose tests defined in the Test Plan Overview covered by this test case (Test ID)	Test 4.1.1, Test 4.1.2, Test 4.1.3 http://bit.ly/ARCHIVER-Test-Plan-Overview
Repository	https://github.com/archiver-project
Contact	Tibor Šimko (tibor.simko@cern.ch) Jakub Urban (jakub.urban@cern.ch)
Test Steps	The prototype shall demonstrate support for plugging in multiple checksum algorithms that may be used in research communities. Example: Adler32 used in the CERN Open Data server.
Test Criteria	The prototype can ingest a dataset using MD5 checksum algorithm and another dataset using Adler32 checksum algorithm. The archive is able to calculate and verify both checksums for data files.
Assessment Criteria	<p>Passed: The Archive is able to ingest an incoming dataset file with Adler32 checksum information. (A blind test variant: the incoming dataset file is not accompanied with any checksum information and the Archive is able to calculate it independently.) The Archive provides an API endpoint returning Adler32 checksum for a desired archived file. The returned checksum matches the original checksum from the CERN Open Data portal.</p> <p>Passed with an issue: The Archive accepts Adler32 checksum for incoming files when provided by the data procedure but is not able to calculate it itself. (The blind test does not pass.)</p> <p>Failed with a workaround: The Archive supports multiple checksum standards, but they are not settable by the user for each concrete file. The user has to contact the Archive administrator or technical support to set desired checksum defaults.</p> <p>Failed: The Archive does not support Adler32 (and MD5) checksums.</p>

Figure 5. - Example of a QA test description including technical assessment criteria.

The Agile development process during the Prototype and Pilot Phases was considered a very effective tactical way of monitoring and adjusting the work plan.

Some of the learnings from the R&D execution activity are the following:

The architectural phase (Design) becomes challenging if very short

This type of project might want to consider simplification of the implementation phases and/or separation of the requirements gathering step in a separate action prior to the PCP. This separation potentially allows to allocate more time to the Design Phase that remains critical to establish the correct baseline of the future R&D to be produced.

Effort to test and validate R&D must be carefully revised.

Even if the public sector organizations participating in the project have estimated the quantity of work needed during the preparation phase of the project, the load remains very significant for iterating of the R&D produced against the uses-cases. In practice, the effort allocated across the public sector organizations and selected companies has been largely above the quantities originally anticipated.

Provision of detailed technical summaries during the project preparation phase.

Before launching the R&D tender, technical descriptions of each of the use-cases included in the project, with information about the desired performance and any technical constraints were found very useful to frame R&D expectations. This includes the identification of a technical responsible, capable of providing technical details about each of the use-cases.

Constant and systematic feedback found essential

Structured communication between public and private sector organizations (in the form of meetings, assessment reports after each milestone, tutorials, webinars, etc.) is key in order to allow full understanding of the R&D challenge and current service capabilities of the selected companies.

Regular sprints in an Agile-like process is found very effective

The organization of R&D with a regular rhythm of feedback and adjustment allows rapid progress. The Agile software development methodology has shown upfront that designs and architectures can only take us so far - when a project progresses and prototypes/pilots are iteratively developed, new information, problems and opportunities come to light.

Part 2: Technical dive in the ARCHIVER resulting services

This part describes the technical services that were selected successfully through all the ARCHIVER R&D phases.

Arkivum SaaS

Arkivum was founded in 2011 out of the University of Southampton with initial focus on Higher Education Research Data and is headquartered in Reading, UK.

During the ARCHIVER project, Arkivum has developed a SaaS solution for long-term data archiving, digital preservation and online access to large research datasets.

The resulting services can be deployed into public or private cloud environments. For cloud deployment, Arkivum has partnered with Google in ARCHIVER, to deploy the solution onto the Google Cloud Platform (GCP). In addition, Arkivum has deployed the solution on premise at CERN to demonstrate portability and show how this can address use cases of data sovereignty.

Figure 6.: - Arkivum fully managed archiving and preservation solution.

Arkivum enables content, which in the case of ARCHIVER included scientific data from a range of sources, to be uploaded, ingested, preserved and made accessible to those who need to use that content in the future (Figure 6). This includes the ability to ingest, validate, organize and manage content as it comes into an archive. The content then goes through appropriate preservation and safeguarding processes, including generating OAIS[14] archiving packages to ensure it is properly protected and remains usable. Content is indexed, searchable, and can be downloaded and exported on-demand. This ensures that the data is searchable, discoverable and accessible for users both today and in the future so people can find and use the content in the archive that they need, when they need it.

Arkivum can provide organizations with a fully hosted SaaS solution that enables them to apply and follow good practices from the Long Term Digital Preservation (LTDP) and Research Data Management (RDM) domains and use the service to help achieve their Research Data Management objectives. This includes applying the Open Archive Information Model (OAIS), following Trusted Digital Repository guidelines and certifications (Trustworthy Digital Repository, CoreTrustSeal[15]) and helping to ensure that research data assets remain FAIR.

The Arkivum resulting services (Figure 7.) were designed to meet all the R&D layers defined by the ARCHIVER challenge.

Specifically, features of the Arkivum SaaS software solution that were developed during ARCHIVER cover the following aspects:

Deployment and Portability

Deployment is cloud-agnostic. Deployments during the project were performed on GCP, however deployment on other cloud providers is possible (e.g. tested by Arkivum on AWS) and on-premise during the project (OpenStack at CERN). This involved significant work to find software components that were portable, scalable and reliable across multiple infrastructures. See the section on knative/keda for more information. The solution uses an agnostic set of deployment and management technologies, including Jenkins, Terraform, Rancher, kubectl, Keda, Kubernetes, Grafana, ELK, Keycloak. Data exports can be done for files and metadata, including dataset round-tripping and transfer of datasets between Arkivum systems. Data and metadata is portable, including support for metadata and data round tripping. The Import/Export of files can be done to/from buckets, including the option to use Bagit. Buckets can be for example AWS, GCP or generic S3 storage for example as provided by MinIO[16]. It is possible to trigger external applications at various stages of the process, e.g. using webhooks after ingesting and exporting datasets. This is done in a platform independent way so it can be used within AWS, GCP or on-prem deployments.

Metadata

A new metadata format (ark-manifest.json) is available resulting from the project R&D activity. This replaces the old ark-file-meta.csv format which was found to be too restrictive. Domain specific metadata schemas (XML and json) are supported along with the ability to define extraction/mapping of metadata to common standards such as DataCite and DublinCore. Support for DataCite relation types[17] allows a user to express relationships between entities such as versioned files, SIPs, AIPs etc. using relations such as *IsNewVersionOf*, *IsObsoletedBy*, *IsOriginalFormOf*, *IsContinuedBy*.

Admins can decide whether to make mandatory metadata in an ingest (ark-manifest.json). Rules can be used to enforce mandatory metadata fields and metadata can be added/updated after files have been ingested. Users can configure and manage their own datapools and metadata namespaces

Data Ingest

Datasets can be ingested that are inside archive files (tar, zip, 7zip etc.). An archive package will be extracted and then the contents ingested, which includes Bagit validation and metadata processing using the new ark-manifest.json format.

Search and Navigation

Content is searchable using metadata, including over API and GUI. Searches can be saved and the results of searches can be easily exported. Hierarchical data structures can be navigated using a Tree View in the UI.

Discovery and Access

The ARCHIVER R&D activities included the Integration with InvenioRDM[18] as a repository front-end allows dataset landing pages to be published and registered with discovery services. In addition, access to archived data is possible through object storage and XRootD[19] protocols. This includes on demand exports to a GCP hosted XRootD server. Data exports can be done for lists of entities (collections, objects, files, metadata, AIPs) so that multiple datasets can be included in an export, or only specific subsets of a dataset are exported. Exports can be done of the files and metadata that match a search. Bulk export is also supported and can be done of files and/or metadata, with/without Bagit, and into user-selected buckets.

Storage Management

Storage of datasets can be done using object lifecycle policies to ensure data storage classes of the underlying storage layer (e.g. GCP standard, nearline, coldline, archive), matching data temperature (access frequency). Retention schedules can be set on entities, e.g. to define a minimum retention period, and notifications are sent to administrators when retention periods expire so that action can be taken such as export or deletion of data. There is automated clean-up support of the buckets that are used for getting data in and out of the solution, e.g. automated deletion of datasets from the upload bucket when ingests are completed and automated deletion of datasets from the export bucket after a defined period of time.

Security, AAI and SSO

Access control is possible using local accounts and IdP integration using eduGAIN. Other SSO integrations are also possible via keycloak. LDAP integration was tested during the project with the help of one of the Buyers (PIC). There is control over what a user can do and the data they can access, which is consistent across UI and APIs. Support for request/approve workflows allows admins to control data access and moderate access requests from end-users, e.g. researchers. The system can be configured to use multiple upload and export buckets. This allows data to be partitioned into different buckets according to workflow or security requirement, both before ingest into the archive and after export from the archive. Penetration testing has been performed by a third-party entity, with results being provided to the ARCHIVER project coordinator (CERN).

Pre and post processing of archive data, support for scientific applications

Scripts and applications could be co-located with archive data in the cloud using a range of GCP services including Cloud Functions, Cloud Run and VMs. This enables software to be deployed into GCP for pre and post processing of archived data using serverless computing, Kubernetes or persistent servers. Webhooks allow these external scripts and applications to be triggered by events in the archive, e.g. completion of ingest, preservation or exports. Scripts and applications have access to a wide range of archive services through the Arkivum REST API, including search and retrieval/export of metadata and data. Scripts and applications can also be run in their own GCP projects and billing accounts, which allows separate cost monitoring and carbon footprint analysis.

The approach of using webhooks and an Arkivum REST API allows the Arkivum solution to be integrated with pre and post processing apps in other cloud infrastructures or on-premises. Whilst GCP was used to host scripts and applications for ARCHIVER R&D validation, similar functionality could be used in AWS such as Lambda or on-premise using OpenStack.

Figure 7.: - Arkivum SaaS architecture resulting from ARCHIVER.

The ARCHIVER solution developed by Arkivum has been tested and shown to address the requirements of archiving and preservation of very large datasets, with high speed ingest and access (Figure 7.), but also with the ability to host and run scientific applications against this data. The features developed were validated against a range of use cases from the ARCHIVER Buyers Group, the Early Adopters, and the wider scientific research community including large research-intensive institutions and the Long-Tail of Science (LToS).

In addition, the resulting services include, as part of their results, support for sustainable long-term digital preservation, such as:

- ☁ a means to achieve economic sustainability with a solution that is cost-effective at scale when working with very large datasets (Figure 8.);
- ☁ ensuring environmental sustainability by minimizing the carbon footprint of the solution and applying good practice in the digital preservation and archiving of research data to ensure sustainable access and reuse of research datasets for the scientific community.
- ☁ Public Total Cost of Service (TCS) modeling calculators to provide the ability to optimize cost taking into consideration data volumes, access frequencies, data safety, data processing and retention periods.
- ☁ the use of open standards, open specifications, open source and open APIs to ensure portability, interoperability, exit strategies and reduction of vendor and solution lock-in.

Ingest and archiving of a 50TB dataset

50,000 HDF5 files (50TB) ingested and stored at a rate of 150TB/day

Figure 8.: - Arkivum SaaS example of scaling demonstrated in ARCHIVER.

Detailed models and commercialization plans that include service level agreements (SLAs), user support, licensing, service configuration and pricing as well as self-assessment as TDR service providers, have been developed during the ARCHIVER project and can be used in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)[20] and beyond.

The table below summarizes the ARCHIVER resulting services provided by Arkivum, considering the 4-Layer R&D scope defined for the project.

ARCHIVER R&D Layer (1-4)

Storage, Basic Archiving,
Secure Backup

System is multi-tenanted.

GEANT network direct peering and NREN connections can be used to ingest and access data.

Ingest rate is over 100TB per day for several of the deployment scenarios.

Access is controlled using SSO and can be integrated with IdPs through eduGAIN.

Deployment in ARCHIVER is on GCP but the deployment approach is cloud agnostic and uses Kubernetes, which allows deployment on other cloud providers (tested on AWS) and on-premise (tested during ARCHIVER on OpenStack at CERN).

ARCHIVER R&D Layer (1- 4)

Data Preservation Archived data is automatically replicated into multiple locations and fixity checked.

Content (data and metadata) can be ingested and exported as individual files or as packages/datasets.

Domain specific metadata schemas are supported along with mapping of metadata to common standards such as DataCite and DublinCore.

OAIS packages are possible using Archivematica which supports bagit, METS and PREMIS.

Data Preservation Use of the system is possible via GUI & API and supports multiple routes for data upload/download including via buckets, REST API and drag and drop in a web browser.

Storage of datasets can be done using object lifecycle policies to ensure data storage classes (e.g. GCP standard, nearline, coldline, archive) match data temperature (access frequency). In other words, users can select different storage options, which have prices linked to the access frequency: for example, infrequently accessed storage is cheaper.

Comprehensive mapping is available to CoreTrustSeal, NDSA levels of preservation, and DPC RAM. This describes how the solution/service implements good practice for LTDP.

User Services Content is searchable using metadata, including over API and GUI.

Metadata can be automatically extracted from files or supplied by users as part of ingested datasets.

Metadata includes support for domain specific schemas, and it is possible to define which metadata fields are indexed and searchable by the solution.

Searches can be saved and the results of searches can be easily exported.

Datasets (files and metadata) can be exported to buckets or exposed through domain specific protocols such as XRootD.

Integration with InvenioRDM as a repository front-end allows dataset landing pages to be published and registered with discovery services.

Access control is possible using local accounts and IdP integration using eduGAIN.

Advanced Services Pre and post processing archive data is possible using cloud-hosted scripts and applications (i.e VMs, Kubernetes, cloud functions, etc). Users are given access directly to the GCP console.

Access to data is possible through generic object storage and XRootD protocols.

Webhooks allow external scripts and applications to be triggered by events in the archive, e.g. completion of ingest, preservation or exports.

Scripts and applications have access to a wide range of archive services through a REST API, including search and retrieval/export of metadata and data.

LIBNOVA (LABDRIVE SaaS)

LIBNOVA is a European SME created in 2009 focused on developing software solutions for Digital Preservation, providing software to ensure secure long-term guaranteed access to information in a simple and efficient manner, without the need to have deep knowledge of technology, full availability and access, making use of Digital Preservation standards, such as ISO 14721 (OAIS) and ISO 16363 (Trustworthy Digital Repository).

In the context of ARCHIVER project, LIBNOVA re-engineered LABDRIVE (Figure 9.), a Research Data Management and Preservation platform that allows organisations to capture the research data they produce, helping them to properly manage, preserve and allow access to it, during the whole data lifecycle.

LIBNOVA's platform allows organisations to transition from a siloed approach in which each series of datasets, departments or units are using multiple, disaggregated systems to keep content to a single repository that can adapt to the particularities of each dataset, unifying all content in a single platform.

Figure 9.: - LABDRIVE SaaS example of scaling demonstrated in ARCHIVER.

The platform works for organizations managing data ranging from a few Gigabytes to several Petabytes. During the ARCHIVER project, the resulting R&D ran on Kubernetes on the AWS cloud, enabling auto-scaling to reduce both cost and carbon footprint. An on-premise installation was demonstrated supporting Openstack at Desy. LABDRIVE was tested to receive 50 million files and 1PB of data in less than 24 hours, scaling itself to more than 6500 Kubernetes pods to process the workload. As depicted in Figure 9., LABDRIVE is formed by a core part complemented by auxiliary services:

☁ LABDRIVE Core: this is the main part of the solution and is composed of 4 different pieces:

- ☁ Services cluster: includes the frontend (the UI that users see) and API servers as well as protocol servers (such as XRootD) and Jupyter kernels.

- ☁ Processing Agents cluster: includes the processing components of the system, in charge of file validation, metadata and property extraction, report generation, integrity assurance, etc.
- ☁ Authentication Provider: groups the SAML-based components in charge of the authentication and authorization services.
- ☁ Services: additional services needed for the correct functioning of the core platform, such as message queues for communication, container orchestration and security.
- ☁ LABDRIVE Auxiliary Services: these services are deployed externally to the main LABDRIVE Core clusters but interact with it and are important for its correct functioning. These could be on-premise or in public clouds and can be heterogeneous services. The main service here is the storage, provided in this case by AWS' S3 (Object Storage). Other services include Elasticsearch (necessary for powerful and fast text searching), databases (which store for example, the metadata schemas), data analytics components (such as Grafana and Prometheus) or compute resources used for reproducibility workloads (i.e a Virtual Machine).

In LABDRIVE, content (represented as files/folders + metadata) lives inside a Data Container. Every object in LABDRIVE is preserved in a Data Container, which is a folder inside an Object Storage bucket (such as an AWS S3 bucket). Containers define the policies, functions, permissions and the underlying storage policy for the files they contain. Hence, content in a given container shares some commonalities like metadata schema, storage policy, permissions, functions, etc. Data Containers are grouped in collections (Figure 10.) or sub collections (archive nodes), creating a way for users to group and organize datasets and content. Depending on their permissions, users/organizations are able to see the whole tree or just a fraction of it. Container functions are able to process files as they are created, periodically or by request. Towards the end of the ARCHIVER project, the possibility to define quotas for containers started to be supported, so access to them was restricted when over quota.

Figure 10.: LIBNOVA's LABDRIVE objects relations and organisation.

The R&D activities of LIBNOVA during the ARCHIVER project included the complete re-engineering and migration to a new architecture to make it scalable to high volumes of data and high throughput.

This has been achieved following an incremental R&D process with the ARCHIVER public sector partners validation, starting at 100k files, then 400k, 1 million, 20 million, 40 million finishing with 140 million consisting of a total of 1,86PB of ingested content. The final tests of LIBNOVA (Figure 11.) allowed a total volume of 15,87 PB ingested representing 618.162.714 files, including 739.416 large files, ingested during 31 days from a LIBNOVA location to AWS in Frankfurt through the GÉANT network at a rate of approximately 500TB every 24 hours. The data ingested was based on the ARCHIVER public organizations datasets, replicated hundreds of times.

LIBNOVA considers that such a volume of ingestion in a preservation system represents a new milestone in the preservation industry, allowing the resulting product of ARCHIVER (a new line of product designated by LABDRIVE Research) to have a new redesigned architecture performing stable with a volume of data 2-3 orders of magnitude better than in the legacy architecture before the ARCHIVER project.

Figure 11. - LIBNOVA's scalability test (15PB, 500TB/day, 618.162.714 files).

In addition, as part of the activities of the ARCHIVER R&D Layer 4, LIBNOVA has built a generic emulation engine into the LABDRIVE software.

This engine was built and designed generically not only to satisfy the science reproducibility requirements of ARCHIVER, but also to be extended as a relevant innovation to other LIBNOVA product lines and customer needs.

The emulation engine has been validated during ARCHIVER by running REANA service[21] workloads, supporting in addition SnakeMake workloads[22] and Jupyter Notebooks[23].

The ARCHIVER-created foundation has been presented at IPRES 2022[24] as a new emulation kernel that allows its customers to run old (obsolescent) software in the preservation platform. LIBNOVA considers this offer as being the first of its kind in the preservation industry.

The generic architecture uses exactly the same technology to satisfy use cases radically different; in addition to reproducibility workloads for scientific data, others examples are obsolete software games or obsolete files (e.g. MSDOS-based WordPerfect files, Lotus 1-2-3 files, etc.) can be used using the original software via the LABDRIVE emulation engine.

Other results of the ARCHIVER R&D activities include the following:

☁ Ingest and reproducibility

- ☁ Improvement of the ingestion workflows
- ☁ Implementation of an abstraction layer in Python (in use in Jupyter Notebooks, Reana, Functions, etc.)
- ☁ a ROOT library has been ported to the LABDRIVE environment, tested to work in the reproducibility cases
- ☁ Jupyter Notebooks support has been extended (user authentication, security model, file system abstraction and metric gathering)
- ☁ XrootD support has been enhanced and can now be parallelized
- ☁ 41 new or improved API methods, virtually every system function is available via API
- ☁ An Object class framework has been improved (also part of the work taking place at EPFL for InvenioRDM/LABDRIVE integration)
- ☁ Preparation of next phase of Reana integration

☁ AAI and Security

- ☁ The Identity Federation module has been improved, matching all identified needs, including automated account creation or automatic account configuration
- ☁ A monitoring framework has been created. All platform logging has been unified using Grafana and Loki
- ☁ Support for quotas management
- ☁ Containers over quota report
- ☁ New functions for structured logging, assets functionality, parameters and selection regex
- ☁ Nginx 1.2 for API reverse proxy support

☁ Metadata and file formats

- ☁ Support of import/export of Metadata schemas
- ☁ Support of a File format ranking database
- ☁ Support of reports for File formats at risk
- ☁ Improvement of security audit and effective permissions reports
- ☁ RabbitMQ-based modules interface (Babel) for Docker Network Segregation (security and performance related)

☁ Performance

- ☁ Development of a dashboard for performance and diagnostics
- ☁ Wonderlord module (Bulk functions for file copy/move/rename) Streams-based Siegfried version
- ☁ Improvements in LABDRIVE Arena to resolve AppArmor/Seccomp incompatibility
- ☁ Modification in several modules for docker rootless execution
- ☁ Archival tree and Container view refactoring for +1M element display
- ☁ User permissions view refactoring for +10.000 users

- ☁ Improved container permission policy management module (container permissions policy pollution)
- ☁ Nuclio pre-fetch improved algorithm
- ☁ The platform CLI, with an initial implementation of three functions required in ARCHIVER has been developed. The tool has been organized in a way we can continue extending it to make it more useful in the future.
- ☁ On-the-fly TAR unpacking function
- ☁ UUID generation concept function
- ☁ Creation of carbon footprint metrics gathering + reports

☁ Documentation

- ☁ New training materials and 800 pages of new documentation have been created, cookbook-oriented explanations and guides, but also curl examples, screen captures, etc. The documentation has been published in a public repository[25].

The LIBNOVA services resulting from the ARCHIVER R&D activity are fully available in the EOSC Marketplace[26]. The table below summarizes the ARCHIVER resulting services provided by LIBNOVA, considering the 4-Layer R&D scope defined for the project.

ARCHIVER R&D Layer (1-4)

Storage, Basic Archiving,
Secure Backup

Capability of handling content of several PBs, with strong foundation to continue improving in the range of hundreds of PB in the future.

The resulting LIBNOVA services can manage large peaks in data traffic and are directly linked to the GÉANT network supporting multi-cloud data storage and an escrow to keep multiple automated replicas of the data.

The solution runs on Kubernetes, regardless of the underlying IaaS. Demonstrated to be installable on AWS and on-prem, deployed at DESY OpenStack on standard VMs (unmanaged Kubernetes cluster).

Storage based on Object Storage, making it possible to migrate to a different provider considering how well established and popular the S3 technology is.

LABDRIVE allows users to access content using multiple protocols: S3 (direct interaction with the Object Storage), SFTP, NFS, rsync, in addition to UI based capabilities. Specifically for the CERN Open Data use case, XRootD support was added (including parallelized jobs), meaning users could upload and download data using the XRootD protocol. Accessing the same data container using multiple protocols is also possible.

LIBNOVA is using standard data packages (BagIt) with full support for data ingestion and retrieval.

Services offer a full set of APIs, not a single byte of information about every preserved object is not accessible using the API, where types of metadata (of all types) can be extracted.

ARCHIVER R&D Layer (1- 4)

Data Preservation

It supports a flexible metadata management mechanism by considering cases in which metadata does not exist along with cases in which complex metadata needs to be preserved.

LABDRIVE manages and preserves content, either to be immediately accessible (hot storage) or that may benefit from a lower storage cost, if frequent access is not needed for it (cold storage).

Mapping of data models and data workflows following FAIR/TRUST.

User Services

Support of complex data type search modes: dates, times, locations, numbers, etc. can all be used for searching. Fulfilling use cases like, "get all datasets belonging to X experiment" with granular search (fields, specific dates, etc.) are supported. Full support for Federated AuthC/Z.

Users are able to define data container-level lambda functions (LABDRIVE Lambda functions) that are executed on certain events. For instance, the user requires LABDRIVE to automatically uncompress every compressed file that is uploaded to the platform, or to perform an automatic validation of every BagIt package uploaded, to get notified every time a user uploads larger datasets or to validate every uploaded file to check if the file is corrupted. All these use cases can be easily resolved with the LABDRIVE Functions allowing an increased flexibility on the interaction with the archived datasets.

Content is organized by collections and sub-collections of data containers. Permissions for content and metadata can be applied at the data container level but also at the collection level (inherited). Users can belong to multiple organizations and can log-in using their own identity provider.

LABDRIVE includes a highly granular permissions schema, including read or read/write permissions to the container level, groups management, etc. Users can log-in using built-in accounts, or using SAML-based authentication schemes involving federated organizations with complex access needs. LABDRIVE includes support for automatic account creation and automatic permissions assignment based on the attributes delivered by the Identity Provider.

LIBNOVA is part of the UK Access Federation[27], so most institutions in the world would be ready to start using its platform with a rather simple configuration.

Smart reports allow the user to get insights about the content on the platform and analyze it. While different reports were added directly to the main UI of the platform, a Grafana/Prometheus (open source components) platform was also deployed and access was granted to the buyers. This increases the monitoring options of the users thanks to the granularity of the user metrics.

ARCHIVER R&D Layer (1- 4)

Advanced Services

Implementation of native Jupyter Notebooks and the creation of a Python SDK. Reana workflows have been integrated to serve as an example to develop a generic reproducibility environment, supporting diverse use cases (ranging from scientific workload reproducibility engines to obsolescent computer games, or application files).

LABDRIVE users do not get access to the underlying IaaS provider (AWS) directly, instead, through LABDRIVE's UI they are able to spin up compute resources.

Additionally, the platform's functions let users run code in the platform, in response to certain events or triggers, without needing any client-side script (similar to Amazon AWS Lambda functions).

Transformational nature of the ARCHIVER legacy

Best Practices and Lessons Learned

Based on the gathered practical experience, a set of lessons learned and best practices can be taken as reference for future PCPs covering aspects such as the procurement process, R&D execution and dissemination of the R&D activities for maximization of results impact by the end of the project.

The highlights can be summarized as follows:

- ☁ Procurement would benefit if reduced in time and complexity, and focussed more on the R&D challenge, as European innovative software SMEs “think” in months rather than years.
- ☁ Structured feedback across all parties is found essential, in order to allow full understanding of the challenge.
- ☁ As previously mentioned, the Agile software development methodology can prove to be very effective if a roadmap for the R&D strategy is produced as a wider frame for expectations, with features prioritization to avoid possible mismatches in the understanding of the challenge.
- ☁ Effort for the tasks of requirement gathering, tender evaluation, assessment and testing of the R&D remains very significant.
- ☁ A dissemination plan articulated between the project participants boosts visibility and reach across different communities, sectors and stakeholders.
- ☁ PCPs for software services would very much benefit from structured incentives to ramp up the results (for example in the EOSC context), sustaining access to the resulting SaaS and fund trials from researchers in view of purchasing the services if trial deployments are successful.

Overall, the project has demonstrated how the PCP instrument can incite European expert SMEs to develop innovative services that can satisfy the needs of Europe’s research communities and paves the way to explore more effectively the integration of commercial services into the EOSC marketplace.

Benefits for public funded research and private sector

The work accomplished in ARCHIVER is considered a game-changer for the approach taken to long-term Research Data Management both from a mindset and technological perspective, i.e. what data do researchers retain, how to keep intellectual control of it and what data stewards must do to ensure long-term value can be realized from it.

The set of innovative services resulting from ARCHIVER are now offered as commodity services via the EOSC exchange service¹[28] as an ecosystem for European specialist ICT companies in archival and preservation services. A key component of sustainability for the PCP results is to ensure the innovation produced is not dormant at the end of the project and has a wide exposure, benefiting potential procurers within the European research community and other business sectors.

As a step to achieve this, the project has started an onboarding process for the resulting services to be available in the EOSC Platform Early Adopters Programme².

1 https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?anchor=&object_id=&q=data+preservation&sort=_score&type=

2 <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-early-adopter-programme>

Another important milestone was the development of a model for facilitating the procurement of pilot-scale, commercially supported services beyond the lifetime of the project both by procurers that were part of the ARCHIVER consortium and organizations that joined the ARCHIVER Early Adopters Programme. The model stimulates the use of the ARCHIVER services available through the EOSC exchange, a form of digital marketplace, giving the possibility to researchers and procuring organizations to have sustainable access to these services, being able to trial them, evaluate their functionality and purchase them with a defined and transparent costing model. A direct consequence of such a model is to substantially raise awareness and up-skilling in archiving and digital preservation of European researchers and citizen scientists tasked with managing the vast and ever-growing datasets generated by world-leading research institutions.

This model is described in public deliverable 5.6 “Sustainability Planning & Strategy”[29].

Another more general upskilling effect comes from the R&D produced during the project itself: more than 50% of the R&D was performed in the EC Member States. This aspect is directly linked to the strategic benefits to the European private sector by participating in ARCHIVER. Prior to the project, the selected SMEs (Arkivum and LIBNOVA) had limited experience of working within public procurement, with limited interaction/traction.

The selected companies have reported very relevant benefits and tangible results for their ARCHIVER activities that include:

- ☁ Shorter development life cycle leading to faster time to market, from 5 to 2 years, giving these participating companies an advantage in relation to other competitors.
- ☁ Increased customer base portfolio not only in Europe but with contracts signed with US universities.
- ☁ Maximization of the understanding of requirements being able to work with multidisciplinary use cases.
- ☁ Pushing the boundaries of what digital preservation is, incorporating innovations that improve the products and empower other organizations to preserve data, consequently creating stronger relationships and incremental business.
- ☁ Partnership agreement with hyperscalers (e.g. AWS and Google) strengthening the business perspectives of these European SMEs.
- ☁ Increase of services sustainability with a special focus on environmental sustainability.
- ☁ Acceleration and de-risking of the ability of these companies to enter a new market with innovative services that addresses the problem of long-term digital preservation and access to scientific research datasets.

These results would not have been possible without their participation in the project. Throughout the project activities, the selected companies have notably expanded areas such as software development, engineering and marketing. This has helped these SMEs to meet the requirements of the project, and seek to maximize promotional impact of the various stages. Both Arkivum and LIBNOVA have seen significant growth of their business turnover since the start of ARCHIVER in several scientific research domains. This is in addition to the funding acquired through the ARCHIVER project itself, such as a reported participation in more than 10 parallel procurements with the results of ARCHIVER.

ARCHIVER has also benefited the gender balance in STEM. The selected companies have reported an increased participation of female employees in the analysis, development, deployment and testing during all three phases of ARCHIVER contributing in various roles for the building of the technological solutions. Due to expansion to new locations such as the USA and Canada, this tendency will be increased in the immediate future to further support the ARCHIVER results in these geographies, specifically for the deployment of the ARCHIVER results on these areas.

Currently, there is no large-scale production usage of commercial data preservation services by the public

research sector. By participating in ARCHIVER, these companies estimate that they gained a lead of at least two years over the competition with the Research and Development process being validated by world leading research organizations.

The ARCHIVER resulting LTDP services were designed and tested to minimize vendor lock-in and encourage the resulting services to stimulate portability and interoperability, yet at the same time making it attractive for new commercial providers to enter the public research sector market, while allowing research organizations to keep the intellectual control of the managed data.

The services resulting from ARCHIVER R&D are addressing the gaps that put data at long-term risk as they prevent the construction and operation of sustainable Trusted Digital Repository services, affecting organizations both large and small who are tasked with being custodians of valuable research artifacts.

Thanks to its outstanding results, the ARCHIVER project has been recognized by the community and been awarded by the International Council on Archives, category for Collaboration and Cooperation[30], at the DPC awards ceremony in Glasgow, on the 12th of September 2022[31].

From a strategic point of view, the work accomplished can be seen as a concrete example of EOSC in practice, providing an innovative vision of how to develop capacity necessary to support the EOSC intended to create a single pan-European market in the digital research space for Europe's millions of researchers, in partnership with the public and European private sector.

To summarize, the ARCHIVER project has accomplished significant work on technological solutions, its economics and business models, in a holistic manner across scientific domains, public/private sectors and geographies, consistent with the evolving Open Science policies in Europe. By working directly with the public sector organizations, Arkivum and LIBNOVA were able to receive ongoing input and feedback into their product development to serve the mission of scientific research within Europe, enabling these SMEs to quickly and effectively develop fit-for-purpose products. This resulted in innovative commercialisation approaches for the resulting services, improving their degree of FAIRness as an aspect of utmost importance for the ultimate objective of reuse of research data.

The focus of initiatives such as ARCHIVER is Data, in particular research data, that is set to live for longer than any vendor, system or technology.

What's next?

The vast majority of new customers of Arkivum and LIBNOVA are using the version of the software benefiting from the work conducted as part of the ARCHIVER project. Both companies also continue to work with their ARCHIVER consortium members to continue the partnership beyond the ARCHIVER project, currently engaged with several markets both within and outside of Europe (e.g. US universities) primarily focused on the research public sector to further growth the commercial success of the project. A clear ambition is to put in practice a procurement model in the context of the EOSC for Long Term Data Preservation services that can effectively expand the reach of the ARCHIVER outputs and consequently generate future opportunities for the resulting services of the PCP, as a key component of sustainability for the PCP results. This will ensure the innovation developed during the project is not dormant at the end of the project and has a wide exposure to potential procurers within the European research community and other business sectors. In addition to the efforts to make the products and services enter into general use, there is work in identifying future opportunities in what concerns additional R&D building on the the results of ARCHIVER in the context of the European Open Science Cloud.

Additional Resources

- [1] <https://archiver-project.eu/>
- [2] <https://www.esfri.eu/forum>
- [3] <http://eosc.eu>
- [4] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4574234>
- [5] https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-SRIA-V1.0_15Feb2021.pdf
- [6] <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/pcp-and-pi-projects>
- [7] <https://projectescape.eu/>
- [8] <https://expands.eu/>
- [9] <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>
- [10] <https://archiver-project.eu/deployment-scenarios>
- [11] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3618215>
- [12] <https://network.geant.org/>
- [13] <https://archiver-project.eu/archiver-open-market-consultation-roadmap>
- [14] <http://www.oais.info/>
- [15] <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>
- [16] <https://min.io/>
- [17] https://support.datacite.org/docs/relaiontype_for_citation
- [18] <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>
- [19] <https://xrootd.slac.stanford.edu/>
- [20] <https://search.eosc-portal.eu/search/service?q=arkivum>
- [21] <https://reanahub.io/>
- [22] <https://github.com/snakemake/snakemake>
- [23] <https://jupyter.org/>
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- [28] <https://search.eosc-portal.eu/search/service?q=arkivum%20libnova>
- [29] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7554802>
- [30] <https://www.dpconline.org/news/dpa2022-winners>
- [31] <https://archiver-project.eu/news/>

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